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Department of Psychology, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur

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Contents

Behavioral Study of Emotionality and Bonding among Teenagers <i>Geetika Mishra and Meenakshi Joshi</i>	1-6
Understanding the Impact of Belief and Narcissism on Magical Ideation among Young Adults <i>Kuvalaya Jain and Sudha Rathore</i>	7-11
Optimism in Relation to Academic Stress among Adolescents <i>Harsha Sharma and Puneet Sharma</i>	12-14
Impact of Korean Drama Culture on Personal Identity, Mental Well-being and Social Values among Young Adults in India <i>Sakshi Garg</i>	15-19
The Impact of Gratitude Practice on the Psychological Well-being among College Students <i>Deepika Jangid, Chhavi Chadha, and Leena Kumari</i>	20-22
Effect of PERMA Model Intervention on Psychological Well-being of School Teachers: An Experimental Study <i>Chiya Jaiswal and O. P. Sharma</i>	23-27
Personality Assessment through Astropsychology: Thematic Apperception Test and Astrological Chart <i>Rishi Bhardwaj and Aditya Pareek</i>	28-34
A Case Report on Overlapping Personality Patterns of Petulant Borderline Personality Disorder and Covert Narcissism in Indian Context <i>Harshika Pareek</i>	35-40
Resilience, and Optimism: A Comparative Analysis of Athletes and Non-Athletes in the Context of Sports Engagement <i>Dinesh Kumar, Rahmath Nishada K., and Guneet Inder Jit Kaur</i>	41-45
Obsessive Compulsive Disorder and Sexual Dysfunction: A Literature Review <i>Prakriti Sharma and Nirmala Singh Rathore</i>	46-48
Psychosocial Factors Related to HIV+ in Selected Tribes across Rajasthan <i>Rahul Saini</i>	49-52
The Relationship between Mindset and Grit among College Students <i>Jothi Lakshmi S. and Ayesha Arif Zinna</i>	53-57
A Review of Interventional Modules for Enhancing Subjective Well-being: Strategies, Outcomes, and Future Directions <i>Garima Yadav</i>	58-60
Study of Preference of Sensory Modality for Relaxation <i>Manisha Gaur, Navendu Gaur, Manaswi Gautam, Shehnaz Khan, and Paridhi Pareek</i>	61-65
Exploring the Association Between Family Cohesion, Cognitive Functioning and Overall Life Contentment in Elder Indian Population <i>Tushita Srivastava</i>	66-70
Exploring the Relationship Between Childhood Trauma and Adolescent Psychopathology: A Correlational Study <i>Tulika Sharma and Asmita Nain</i>	71-77

Contents

Well-being and Stress among Police Personnel <i>Anjana Choudhary, Neha Kalia, and O.P. Sharma</i>	78-83
Effects of Bedtime Procrastination on Young Adults Well-being: A Comprehensive Exploration of Emotional Regulation, Self-compassion, and Self-regulation <i>Anupriya Narika</i>	84-88
Psychological Well-being as a Route to Social Bonding among Adolescents <i>Matrika Singh</i>	89-93
Exploring the Relationship between GRIT, Gratitude and Mental Health among Secondary School Students: A Quantitative Study <i>Dimple Sharma and Hema Kumari Mehar</i>	94-96
Impact of Forced Single-parent and Single-parent Families on Mental Health of College Students <i>Meena, Madhu Lata Nayal, and Vallari Kukreti</i>	97-102
Cultural Impact: Perceived Parenting Style on Adult Attachment and Love Attitude in College Students <i>Harsh Barve and Shivika Patel</i>	103-107
Exploring the Relationship of Body Image, Conformity, and Self-esteem with Style and Fashion Clothing Orientations <i>Mahima Choudhary</i>	108-112
Exploring Socio-cultural Dynamics: Attachment Styles of Married Men in their Relationships <i>Shivika Patel and Harsh Barve</i>	113-117
Personality and Emotional Intelligence among School Going Children: A Quest of Some Psycho-social Correlates <i>Mir Zafar Iqbal and Syed Muntaha Shahab Andrabi</i>	118-124
Effect of Interventions on Sustained Attention for an Autistic Student: A Case Study <i>Archana Soni and Preet Kamal</i>	125-131
Therapeutic Elements in Selected Folk Dances of India <i>Chirmi Acharya and Komal Surana</i>	132-134
Exploring the Preparedness of Health and Wellness Centres for Mental Health Promotion and Prevention Strategies <i>Mamta Chauhan, Nishanka Chauhan, and Archana Saxena</i>	135-139
Impact of Nature of work on Life Satisfaction among Government Primary School Teachers and Government Administrative Staff <i>Bhawana, Kamala D. Bhardwaj, and Madhu Lata Nayal</i>	140-143

Effect of PERMA Model Intervention on Psychological Well-being of School Teachers: An Experimental Study

Chiya Jaiswal¹ and O. P. Sharma²

Department of Psychology, University of Rajasthan, JLN Marg, Jaipur, Rajasthan¹
Department of Psychology, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan²

Teaching is often considered one of the most noble and revered professions globally. The Psychological Well-being of the teachers is very important as it not only impacts their own lives but also the lives of their students. Present study aimed to study the effect of PERMA model on Psychological Well-being of teachers classified into experimental and control groups. It is an experimental study conducted using Solomon's 4 group design. In the present study, 6 groups were formed with 15 males and 15 females in each group. The experimental groups' subjects received the PERMA model intervention for 2 weeks. T-test will be used to compare the experimental and control groups to see if there is any effect of PERMA model intervention on the subjects.

Keywords: PERMA model, intervention, psychological well-being, teachers

Psychological Well-being (PWB) refers to a state of overall mental health and satisfaction with life. The concept of mental well-being is closely tied to positive mental health, encompassing feelings of happiness, a strong sense of self and positive attitudes towards oneself and others. Singer and Ryff (1998) emphasize that happiness is an expression of one's life and is indicative of psychological health. Psychologically healthy individuals exhibit independence, self-control, and actively seek environments that align with their needs. They set clear life objectives and strive for personal exploration and development.

Research suggests that individuals in middle age tend to exhibit greater well-being compared to both elderly and young adults. Psychological well-being includes cognitive judgments like life satisfaction and emotional responses such as positive emotions (Diener, 2000). It encompasses various aspects of everyday experiences, including thoughts, emotions, behavior, and choices that reflect an individual's state of mind.

Ryff's Psychological Well-being model provides a framework that emphasizes eudemonic measures, focusing on deeper aspects of well-being such as meaning, optimum functioning, and quality of life. The model comprises six dimensions: autonomy, positive relationships with others, purpose in life, self-acceptance, mastery of the environment, and personal growth. These dimensions contribute to the overall well-being.

Maintaining mental well-being is crucial for effective performance in both personal and professional life, especially for

teachers. Career choices should be informed by proper career counseling and psychological evaluations, including aptitude tests and assessments of attitudes, interests, or intelligence. Career decisions based on these evaluations can reduce the risk of unhappiness or diminished mental well-being due to an incompatible career choice.

Positive Psychological Well-being (PWB) stands at the forefront of contemporary psychological research, representing a paradigm shift from traditional deficit-focused approaches to a more holistic understanding of mental health and overall life satisfaction. PWB is a multifaceted construct that encompasses various dimensions contributing to individuals' overall sense of fulfillment and life satisfaction. Unlike earlier models that primarily focused on diagnosing and treating mental disorders, the positive psychology movement, of which PWB is a central concept, seeks to explore and cultivate the positive aspects of human experience.

Significance of Positive Psychological Well-being

Shift from Pathology to Flourishing: The significance of Positive Psychological Well-Being lies in its departure from the traditional disease model of mental health. Rather than solely addressing symptoms and disorders, PWB shifts the focus towards fostering individuals' flourishing, encompassing positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment.

Enhanced Life Satisfaction: PWB is intrinsically tied to life satisfaction and overall happiness. Individuals with high levels of PWB are more likely to have a larger sense of purpose, positive emotions, and a general satisfaction with their lives.

Resilience and Coping: Positively psychologically well individuals tend to demonstrate greater resilience in the face of challenges. They possess a repertoire of coping mechanisms, drawing on strengths and positive emotions to navigate life's complexities more effectively.

Improved Physical Health: Studies suggest that there is a bidirectional relationship between PWB and physical health. Positive psychological states have been associated with better health outcomes, indicating that mental well-being extends beyond the psychological realm to influence physical health.

Author Note

¹Chiya Jaiswal, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
JLN Marg, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan
²O. P. Sharma, Head & Professor, Department of Psychology
University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan
E-mail: opbrd65@gmail.com

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Chiya Jaiswal, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
JLN Marg, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan
E-mail: studypsychologywithchiya@gmail.com

Productivity and Creativity: Individuals with a high level of Positive Psychological Well-being often exhibit increased productivity and creativity. Engaged and motivated individuals are more likely to approach tasks with enthusiasm, leading to enhanced performance and innovative problem-solving.

Positive Social Relationships: Positive Psychological Well-being contributes to the establishment and maintenance of fulfilling social connections. Individuals who experience positive emotions and engage meaningfully with others are more likely to build and sustain positive relationships, which, in turn, further enhance their well-being.

Educational and Occupational Success: PWB is associated with notable implications for both educational and occupational accomplishments. Studies indicate that individuals with elevated levels of well-being tend to perform exceptionally well academically, achieve success in their careers, and enjoy heightened job satisfaction.

In a nut shell, Positive Psychological Well-being represents a paradigm shift in the area of psychology, emphasizing the importance of positive experiences and optimal functioning in individuals' lives. Recognizing and enhancing PWB holds profound implications for mental health, life satisfaction, and the overall quality of human existence.

PERMA model

The PERMA model is a psychological theory developed by Martin Seligman, a prominent psychologist and the founder of positive psychology. Seligman introduced this model in his book "Flourish: A Visionary New Understanding of Happiness and Well-being," published in 2011. The PERMA model outlines five essential elements which contribute to a person's overall well-being and life satisfaction:

Positive Emotions (P): This component centers around positive emotions, including joy, gratitude, love, and contentment. The cultivation of positive emotions is a fundamental element of well-being. Engaging in activities like spending time with loved ones, pursuing hobbies, or practicing mindfulness supports the experience of happiness. Positive emotions, rooted in positive psychology, emphasize the development and encounter of positive emotional states like happiness, gratitude, love, or contentment. Beyond immediate well-being, positive emotions play a crucial role in long-term psychological and physical health. They act as foundational elements for resilience, creativity, and overall life satisfaction.

Engagement (E): An engagement, also referred to as "flow", involves being fully immersed and absorbed into the activity. People often lose track of time and feel a great sense of satisfaction when they are involved. This may take place during work, hobby or any activity that enables individuals to exploit their strengths and skills. Engagement, often associated with the concept of "flow" introduced by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, involves being fully immersed and absorbed in an activity. The theoretical foundation lies in the idea that engaging in activities that align with one's strengths and interests promotes optimal functioning and a sense of fulfillment.

Relationships (R): Social ties and positive relationships are essential for well-being. Nurturing and maintaining good relationships with family, friends, and community members contribute significantly to happiness and life satisfaction. Building strong social support networks is seen as an essential component of overall well-being. The relationship element is based on social psychology and

attachment theory, and emphasizes the importance of positive social connections. In response to research showing the impact of social support on mental and physical health, meaningful relationships are regarded as essential for human well-being. Supportive, positive relationships provide psychological security, encourage a sense of identity and contribute to life satisfaction in all respects.

Meaning (M): It is essential for good health that we find a sense of purpose and meaning in life. Understanding one's values and goals, as well as the alignment of daily activities with them, is part of that process. Meaningful activities may include pursuing personal goals, contributing to a cause, or engaging in activities that align with one's values and beliefs. The Meaning element focuses on the pursuit and realization of a sense of purpose and significance in life, deriving from existential psychology and positive psychology. Theoretical perspectives include Viktor Frankl's logotherapy, which highlights the importance of finding meaning in life's difficulties. Individuals who find purpose in their actions and align their activities with personal values experience a deeper sense of fulfillment.

Accomplishment (A): The achievement of goals and a sense of accomplishment contribute to well-being. Setting and achieving realistic goals, whether personal or professional, provides a sense of competence and satisfaction. Celebrating achievements, no matter how small, can positively impact one's overall well-being. Grounded in achievement motivation theories, the Accomplishment element centers on the pursuit and attainment of goals. Theoretical perspectives include self-determination theory, emphasizing the importance of setting and achieving personally meaningful goals for intrinsic motivation. Accomplishing goals contributes to a positive sense of self-efficacy, competence, and motivation. Celebrating achievements, whether big or small, enhances overall well-being and contributes to a positive outlook on life.

The PERMA model suggests that a combination of these five elements contributes to lasting well-being and life satisfaction. The model has been widely used in positive psychology research and interventions to enhance individuals' overall well-being. This model is closely associated with the concept of Positive Psychological Well-Being (PWB). In fact, one of the primary goals of the PERMA model is to enhance overall well-being, and it aligns with the broader positive psychology movement, which seeks to promote optimal functioning and flourishing in individuals.

Objective of the Study

To study the effect of PERMA model on Psychological Well-being of teachers classified into experimental group and control group.

Hypothesis of the Study

There would be a positive impact of PERMA model on Psychological Well-being of teachers in the experimental group in relation with the control group.

Variables

- Independent Variable PERMA model intervention
- Dependent Variable Psychological Well-being
- Dependent Variable Psychological Well-being

Method

Participants

120 teachers working in private schools were selected for the present

study using purposive sampling. 60 males and 60 females teachers were selected working in both urban and rural areas from the states of Rajasthan and Gujarat. They were classified randomly into four groups- 2 experimental and 2 control groups with 15 males and 15 females in each group.

Inclusion Criteria: Both males and females teachers working in private schools in both urban and rural areas (age range 25 to 35), were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: The study excluded physically handicapped and psychologically disordered teachers, with an age range restriction from below 25 to above 35 years. It also excluded teachers from government schools, concentrating on those from private or non-government schools. These exclusions were made to define a specific group of teachers for the study, aligning with the research objectives.

Research Design

To study the objectives of the study, following statistics were used to analyze the obtained data. Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and t-test were computed to find out the significance of difference in the

experimental and control groups.

Measure

Psychological Well-being Scale (Ryff, 2007): Ryff developed the Psychological well-being scale (Revised Form) for measuring psychological well-being. The scale contains 42 items with six-point rating options. It covers six dimensions of psychological well-being. Its test-retest reliability is > .80.

Procedure

The study was experimental in nature. It was conducted whereby the subjects were listed as per the criteria inclusion and exclusion of the study. After obtaining consent from the subjects, the psychological measure of the study was sent via Google Forms. Pre data was collected for EG₁ and CG₁. 2 weeks long PERMA model intervention were given to the experimental groups' subjects. The PERMA model intervention plan is shown in Table 1. After the intervention, both EG₁ and CG₁ participants were re-assessed for their levels of PWB. While the EG₂ and CG₂ participants were not given any pretest but only assessed post-test. Eg₂ received the intervention while the CG₂ did not.

Table 1
PERMA Model Plan

Subject	Intervention content
Rapport building and understanding PWB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introducing self and subjects introduce themselves. Rapport building
Discovering positive psychological qualities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explaining the concepts of Positive Psychology, PWB and others The technique of speaking to understand the psycho-emotional state Analyze the problems faced By encouraging participants to share positive and happy things about themselves, they will be able to take advantage of their positive psychological qualities.
Cultivate positive emotions (P)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive thinking and a positive attitude toward life are to be cultivated, it was recommended to watch films that have positive themes. For the positive emotions of the participants, recognize and praise them.
Gratitude (P)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advise them to focus on positive aspects in their lives. Encourage the practice of documenting three positive occurrences each day before bedtime, either in a diary or sharing with friends,
preferably on a daily basis. Engagement (E)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the concept and positive impacts of the "flow" state. Discuss participants' hobbies and interests, encouraging participation when possible. Discuss the importance of positive communication skills and their contribution to fostering interpersonal relationships. Communicate the benefits of interpersonal relationships, citing examples of physical and psychological advantages.
Foster Positive Interpersonal Relationships (R)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore the significance of life, existence, loved ones, and health, guiding individuals to form a correct perspective on meaning. Explore the significance of each individual's role within the family and its importance to loved ones, friends, and society.
Perception Meaning (M)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage self-evaluation and encourage individuals to articulate their understanding of meaning. Suggest exploring literature on existential psychology.
Experience the achievement (A)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provided an opportunity to share personal accomplishments in any area of life. Recognized and commended their achievements. Motivated the creation of a "To-Do calendar" with achievable daily and weekly goals, suggesting celebrating self-accomplishments after three consecutive task completions.

Results

In trying to study the actual study hypothesis, overall descriptive statistics like Mean and Standard Deviation were calculated. Solomon's 4 group design was used and hence there were two experimental and two control groups. EG₁ and CG₁ underwent pre and posttest while the EG₂ and CG₂ went only posttest. PERMA model intervention was given to both EG₁ and EG₂. There were total 120 participants in the study divided equally in all the four groups. Degree of freedom for each group was, therefore, 29. EG₁ had a mean and SD of 94.9 and 3.1 respectively pretest while CG₁ had a mean of 92.83 and SD of 3.85, pretest. EG₁ had a mean and SD of 134.63 and 16.22 respectively posttest while CG₁ had a mean of 94.07 and SD of

3.56, posttest. The mean and SD values were 119.23 and 12. for EG₂ and 94 and 3.58 for CG₂, respectively, posttest.

From Table I, it can be observed that the independent sample t-test value of EG₁ and CG₁ for pre-test is 0.84281 and the p-value is 0.201399 which is found to be not significant at 0.01 level showing that the groups are comparable and not at variance from each other. After PERMA model intervention was given, posttest was done for both the groups and it was found that the t-value came out to be 13.37708 with p-value less than 0.00001, making it significant at 0.01 level. EG₂ and CG₂ underwent posttest only and their t-test value was found to be 11.03466 with p-value less than 0.00001, making it significant at 0.01 level.

Table I

t-test Calculations for Independent Means

Test	df	t	p	Significance level	Interpretation
Pre test (EG ₁ & CG ₁)	29	0.84281	.201399	0.01	Not significant
Post test (EG ₁ & CG ₁)	29	13.37708	<.00001	0.01	Significant
Post test (EG ₂ & CG ₂)	29	11.03466	<.00001	0.01	Significant

From Table II, we can see that when EG₁ was compared pretest and posttest, the dependent t-test value came out to be 12.888471 with p-value less than 0.00001 which shows significant difference at 0.01

level. The dependent t-test value of CG₁, when compared pretest and posttest, yielded 0.301659 with p-value of 0.76506 which shows no significant difference at 0.01 level.

Table II

t-test Calculations for Dependent Means

Group	df	t	p	Significance level	Interpretation
EG ₁ (pre & posttest)	29	12.888471	<.00001	0.01	Significant
CG ₁ (pre & posttest)	29	0.301659	0.76506	0.01	Not significant

EG₁ had a mean and SD of 134.63 and 16.22 respectively pretest while CG₁ had a mean of 94.07 and SD of 3.56, posttest. The mean and SD values were 119.23 and 12 for EG₂ and 94 and 3.58 for CG₂, respectively, posttest. This shows that the EG₁ was sensitized due to the pre-test.

worked in private schools. Government school teachers can also be included in further researches. Teachers working in colleges and universities can also be included in the study. Along with Psychological well-being, subjective well-being can also be studied in future researches. Gender differences can also be studied.

Conclusion

The t-test value indicates that there is a significant difference in the levels of Psychological Well-Being of the Experimental Groups' subjects when compared pre and post PERMA model Intervention. This proves that the hypothesis formulated was true.

Limitations and Ideas for Further Study

The research took place in the state of Rajasthan and Gujarat only in India. So, it is crucial to cover other regions as well to get a diverse picture. Also, there were 120 school teachers of secondary level in the present study. A larger sample can be used. The sample belonged to the age range of 25 to 35. Further studies can involve teachers of more age groups and can compare them too. Teachers in this study

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